

PROBLEMS OF INFLUENCE OF ISLAM ON CONSCIOUSNESS TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract. The article analyzes information on the Islamic religion and its introduction to Central Asia, its main features of the Eastern Renaissance, New Uzbekistan and today's spiritual issues.

Keywords: Islam, spiritual purification, spiritual and moral principles, mysticism, science.

The introduction of Islam to Central Asia created conditions for expanding the scope of scientific research and interest in religious and secular knowledge in the region. At the same time, Islam is characterized by a significant impact on the transformation of consciousness. In its place, the teaching of Islam rejects guluw. It calls for compliance with the rules of the norm. It is characterized by the fact that it is fully compatible with "Quantity change to quality change" and is of great importance in the formation of a pragmatic worldview. This caused the beginning of the Eastern Renaissance in the region (during the 9th-11th centuries Europe was backward). In particular, the historical-philosophical principles created by Farabi, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Farghani and others in the way of science served as a great impetus not only for the peoples of the region, but also for the development of science in the whole world [1]. Already, spiritual purification is an indispensable spiritual and moral principle of our New Uzbekistan, which is boldly stepping into the Third Renaissance. Similar ideas are also important in Islam and Sufism. So, the development strategy of our country and the tenets of Islam and Sufism are in common with each other. All of them are fully compatible with the correct orientation of education, such as universalism, patriotism, enlightenment, humanitarianism. After all, in the following years, the increased attention to the freedom of belief, the Holy Quran and the science of Hadith will not fail to have a positive effect on the above education effect. From the methodological point of view, we witness that the feeling of loyalty to the Motherland is highlighted in social philosophy based on the formative approach to the development of society. Because it pays attention to spiritual principles and makes it possible to take into account all aspects of spirituality. In particular, great scholars such as Imam Bukhari, Najmuddin Kubro, Naqshbandi, At-Tirmizi, Motrudi, Marginani, Khoja Ahror Vali, who are of special importance in the development of Islam, skillfully explained both

religious and worldly aspects of the principle of loyalty to the Motherland in their scientific and spiritual heritage.

We know that the religion of Islam has consistently propagated the ideas of humanity and patriotism since time immemorial. called the peoples of the world to mutual harmony and cooperation, and encouraged them to resolve any disputes peacefully. The religion of Islam, which has been preserved for centuries, has remained stable until our time, and it should be left in this state to the future generations after us.

Creation of foundations of civil society, i.e. self-government of citizens, liberalization of activities of political parties, economic system and its formation based on free market relations is an example of the implementation of the concept of a strong state to a strong society.

Currently, there is a growing need for examples of historical and spiritual experience that can be a sufficient basis for ensuring economic, social and political stability, spiritual and educational growth, and ensuring the rule of law in all areas of development and progress. This encourages us to study the examples of our past spiritual heritage again and again and to use them properly in creating the foundations of a great state-civil society in the future.

Abdurahim Erkaev, a philosopher-scientist on the issues of homeland and human value, expressed great ideas in the process of globalization. That is, "Spiritual development depends not only on material and cultural development, but also on the expansion of people's worldview, religious faith, scientific, artistic, intellectual, legal and moral awareness." In his views, the teacher tries to interpret spirituality in a truly philosophical way. According to him, any law, relationship, necessity is based on the norm. If the norm is violated, the law does not work. Adherence to norms is extremely important in determining the place of forms of social consciousness in the system of spirituality [2]. Today, in any country that wants to achieve development, it is necessary to consider a person and his dignity and honor at the level of state policy. In general, a complex system of modern human image development is being developed. From the methodological point of view, we witness that the feeling of loyalty to the Motherland is highlighted in social philosophy based on the formative approach to the development of society. Because it pays attention to spiritual principles and makes it possible to take into account all aspects of spirituality. In particular, great scholars such as Imam Bukhari, Najmuddin Kubro, Naqshbandi, At-Tirmizi, Motrudi, Marginani, Khoja Ahror Vali, who are of special importance in the development of Islam, skillfully explained both religious and worldly

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person's spiritual maturity lies love for the land where his navel blood was spilled, harmony with Mother Nature in his soul" [3] - states the conclusion. Such views of the scientist can be evaluated as a natural transformation of the personality in the formation of consciousness. At the same time, it should not be forgotten that the importance of social reforms in forming people's attitude towards the Motherland is incomparable. Especially in recent years, the fact that people see and feel the reforms around them with their own eyes ensures the formation of a new worldview. In this context, the implementation of the principle that "the people do not serve the state agencies, but the state agencies serve our people", people enter into open communication with state officials and express their will directly, and the said suggestions and problems are solved in this place are socially important for people. It is observed that it serves to further increase the activity. It can be recognized as a real example of openness and pragmatic management in our country.

Today, a lot can be said about the noble work aimed at finding a way to people's hearts, listening to their pains and concerns, and looking for solutions to their problems. So, where do these virtues and good initiatives get their energy? Of course, from the heart! From the sense of belonging to the country and the people! It was not for nothing that Hazrat Navoi said that "he who joins Elga finds his life".

The reforms carried out to preserve and strengthen the independence of the country, moreover, regarding the high resilience of our people, philosopher and scientist N. Joraev, "Improving society, enriching the population's outlook and understanding with new ideas is a long-term process. Or, in other words, it is the programming activity of Uzbekistan in the new century. At a time when complex, conflicting, large-scale reforms such as the transitional period are in full swing, maintaining consistency in state administration, carrying out the difficult and good things that have been started and bringing them to an end is of great importance in the life of society and citizens" [4] - expresses his thoughts. It can be seen that the principle of loyalty to the motherland achieves a more effective result in the mutual integration of the individual, society and the state.

During the following years, the intensity of the updates that took place in Uzbekistan aroused great interest in the world community. In turn, the achieved results are highly recognized. Because there is no sector that has not been reformed. A new image is added to the image of cities and villages, people's thinking, outlook, and lifestyle are also changing. The most important thing is that our people understand the essence of the policy being conducted today. Increased sense of belonging. Everyone is witnessing that bold steps are being

taken from national revival to national rise. That's why there are many people who are eager to contribute to the changes. Of course, no matter how high the goals are, no matter how promising the projects are, they cannot be implemented without dedicated people who love the Motherland and work wholeheartedly. Thankfully, we have many examples worth bragging about. We have every right to say that the ranks of our true patriots are very wide. During the discussion about spirituality, spiritualist scientist Imomnazarov M. We think it is appropriate to share your thoughts. In the views of the scientist, the Person is primary, "The Person is at the center of spirituality. Spirituality does not exist outside of the individual, because it is the divine light reflected in the human heart, the light of the Supreme Truth - he says. His psyche is formed in this space, this country is considered his Motherland, and a spiritual relationship with him arises in the world of the soul. It is difficult to imagine a person who does not have the feeling of the Motherland as a person. ... at the beginning of a person's spiritual maturity lies love for the land where his navel blood was spilled, harmony with Mother Nature in his soul" [3] - states the conclusion. Such views of the scientist can be evaluated as a natural transformation of the personality in the formation of consciousness. At the same time, it should not be forgotten that the importance of social reforms in forming people's attitude towards the Motherland is incomparable. Especially in recent years, the fact that people see and feel the reforms around them with their own eyes ensures the formation of a new worldview. In this context, the implementation of the principle that "the people do not serve the state agencies, but the state agencies serve our people", people enter into open communication with state officials and express their will directly, and the said suggestions and problems are solved in this place are socially important for people. it is observed that it serves to further increase the activity. It can be recognized as a real example of openness and pragmatic management in our country.

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